

A Comparative Study of the Number of Existing Water Bodies in and around Sunderbans

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Abstract

West Bengal ranks first among the Indian states regarding the existing number of water bodies. Among the districts, South 24 Parganas houses the highest number of water bodies. The majority of South 24 Parganas district is part of the Sunderbans delta region. Objective of this study is to compare number of enumerated water bodies, at the country, state and district levels as well as an analysis of districts in West Bengal with the highest number of water bodies recorded. The analysis reveals that there is a big gap between total number of water bodies in existence in South 24 Parganas and the runner up districts. Another motif of this study is to find appropriate causes behind.

Keywords: Existing water bodies, First Census Report, In-use water bodies, Ponds, Sunderbans.

Introduction

West Bengal has the highest number of water bodies in rural and urban areas of any state in the country [1]. Among all the districts of India, South 24 Parganas ranks first in at least one respect and that is the largest number of water bodies in the district (Table 1). The district's success in being the first in the first census report in the country on water bodies appears to be reflected. Water bodies have been censused mainly in freshwater bodies like ponds, tanks, lakes etc. surrounded by land. The Census report states that West Bengal has the largest number of ponds and reservoirs, while Andhra Pradesh is the leading state for containing tanks, Tamil Nadu has the largest number of lakes, and Maharashtra has the largest number of water reservoirs under conservation schemes.

Table 1. The number of existing water bodies in the top 15 districts in West Bengal.

Rank	District	Existing
1	South 24 Parganas	355780
2	Howrah	37301
3	Paschim Medinipur	35467
4	Birbhum	33968
5	North 24 Parganas	33867
6	Purba Barddhaman	33181
7	Dakshin Dinajpur	30939
8	Hugli	26894
9	Purba Medinipur	25952
10	Bankura	24846
11	Koch Bihar	21881
12	Purulia	20867
13	Murshidabad	18674
14	Nadia	13874
15	Malda	11903

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Currently, the total number of water bodies in the country is 24,24,540, out of which West Bengal holds the first position with 7,47,480 water bodies. Out of the total 7,47,480 water bodies in the state, South 24 Parganas district alone has 3,55,780, making this district the first in the country. Again, in terms of number of usable water bodies, South 24 Parganas district has occupied the first position although the numbers of existing (3,55,780) and usable (3,55,503) water bodies for this district are not the same [2]. 1.6% of water bodies out of all the enumerated water bodies have been reported to be encroached, however, 0 (zero) of those encroached water bodies belong to the South 24 Parganas district (Table 4).

Table 2. The number of in-use water bodies in the top 15 districts in West Bengal.

Rank	District	In-use
1	South 24 Parganas	355503
2	Paschim Medinipur	32064
3	North 24 Parganas	30297
4	Purba Barddhaman	29846
5	Howrah	29557
6	Dakshin Dinajpur	28091
7	Birbhum	27752
8	Purba Medinipur	24499
9	Bankura	23010
10	Hugli	21354
11	Koch Bihar	21148
12	Purulia	18836
13	Murshidabad	16301
14	Nadia	11246
15	Malda	11118

Analysis & Discussions

On a larger scale, a comparison may be drawn between the number of existing and in-use water bodies across the top 15 districts in West Bengal. In both instances, the same 15 district names come up, and although South 24 Parganas retains the first position by a noteworthy margin in both cases, the other districts experience some shuffling among themselves (Tables 1 & 2). The steep drop off is the number of water bodies is not unnatural but mostly due to geographical effect. In such a situation, any inference drawn from the variances or standard deviations of the recorded data will be illogical given the expected

outcomes would be very high (Table 3). The noticeable difference between the arithmetic mean and the median, characterized by the high values of sample variance and sample standard deviation may again be considered as effective results of geographical, demographical, and occupational disparity. On a side note, it is commendable that almost 94% of the total enumerated water bodies among the top fifteen districts in West Bengal are being actively utilized.

Table 3. Statistics of the existing & in-use water bodies in the top 15 districts in West Bengal.

Water Bodies	Existing	In-use
Mean	48359.6	45374.8
Median	26894	24499
Sample Variance	7294223662	7405176728
Sample SD	85406.2273	86053.3365

Most of the water bodies are used in pisciculture, followed by irrigation, ground water recharge and domestic/drinking purpose. In the Sunderbans area, the main occupation is farming. Farming in this case refers to crop farming and fish farming as well as animal husbandry [3]. Unsurprisingly, South 24 Parganas ranks first in the total number of water bodies being used for pisciculture in India. The extremely saline nature of the delta region means that artificial water bodies, or man-made enclosures of water have to be created to farming freshwater fish and irrigation purposes. An astounding 100% of waterbodies enumerated in South 24 Parganas as well as the state of West Bengal are man-made according to the report data (Table 4) [2]. These significantly contribute to the rejection of the prior hypothesis that the sudden drop off in number of water bodies recorded in the top 15 districts in West Bengal in the census was due to geographical disparity. A new deduction is required in this regard. Demography might express a notable causal relationship since the popular occupation of the districts must vary significantly, the utilization of water bodies being few and far between, but it is definitely nowhere near an ultimatum.

The water bodies that have been labelled as “not in use” have mostly dried up (due to

Table 4. Distributional classification of water bodies in South 24 Parganas, West Bengal & India.

Water Bodies	India	West Bengal	South 24 Parganas
Total Existing	2424540	747480	355780
In-use	2030040	698944	355503
Man-made	1890463	747480	355780
Encroached	38496	0	0

construction or siltation), destroyed beyond repair, express salinity beyond usable limits, and other reasons. Attention may be drawn to the Santragachi Jheel in this regard. The water body had been in such a suspended state (overwhelmed by eutrophication) that a significant decline in migratory birds had been observed. However, due to recent intervention, the water body has regained rejuvenation and a subtle yet important increase in bird numbers was recorded in 2023 [4].

Out of the 1442993 ponds in India, West Bengal alone houses 410083 ponds that are in-use and at this point, it is common sense that South 24 Parganas must be home to the majority of those. One of the main reasons for the abundance of ponds in South 24 Parganas district is the relatively low-lying settlement. However, the settlement was at a higher elevation than the normal flood line in the district because most of the areas belong to the Sunderbans [5]. Then the population pressure gradually increased in this district. As human technological knowledge expanded, people learned to artificially raise low-lying areas. And then settlements expanded to the relatively low-lying areas of the plains. Humans have dug holes in the soil of low-lying land while raising the habitat artificially. People's beauty-thirsty mind has turned the hollow hole into a pond with a beautiful shape. The pond water

is used for their fish farming. Then the pond became part of their culture. Ponds have been incorporated as new elements in the evolution of human settlements. Those ponds are being encroached upon by urban development due to which the number of ponds is gradually decreasing in the district of 24 Parganas along with other districts in the country [6].

References

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